

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi Tam Metinleri
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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşecektir. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 12 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Fas, Irak, Katar, Kazakistan, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 73'ü Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 77'si farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 150 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildirilere ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Akyüz
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يسرنا أن نقدم لكم هذا الكتاب الذي يضم مجموعة الأبحاث الكاملة التي قُدمت خلال فعاليات المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، الذي عُقد في العاصمة التركية أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. كان هذا المؤتمر فرصة مميزة لتبادل الأفكار والمعرفة بين نخبة من الباحثين والأكاديميين المتخصصين في مجالات الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، حيث تميز بالتنوع الفكري والتخصصي الذي يعكس تطور هذه المجالات الحيوية.

شهد المؤتمر مشاركات واسعة من باحثين من مختلف الجامعات والمؤسسات العلمية حول العالم، وأسهم في مناقشة العديد من القضايا المحورية التي تتعلق بالتحديات الاجتماعية والقانونية التي تواجه المجتمعات المعاصرة. كما تناولت الأبحاث المقدمة مواضيع تتعلق بالتاريخ وارتباطه بتشكيل البنى الاجتماعية والقانونية في الحاضر، مما أضفى بعداً تحليلياً معمقاً على المناقشات العلمية.

إن هذا الكتاب يضم بين دفتيه نتاج جهود بحثية متميزة أسهمت في تقديم رؤى نقدية ومعرفية حول قضايا متشابكة ومعقدة، مع السعي إلى تقديم حلول مستدامة للتحديات القانونية والاجتماعية القائمة. ولعل هذا التنوع في الأبحاث يعكس مدى أهمية المؤتمر في تعزيز التفاهم العلمي وتوسيع آفاق الحوار الأكاديمي بين الباحثين في مختلف التخصصات. نتمنى أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة قيمة إلى المعرفة العلمية، وأن يساهم في تطوير الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية بما يعزز التقدم الفكري والاجتماعي للمجتمعات.

أنقرة – 2024/10/12

رئيس المؤتمر

- Modern Dünyanın Kötülük Probleminin Kaynağı Olarak Medya.....702**
Doç. Dr. Ali Yıldırım
- Simülasyon ve Dijital İkiz Kavramının Dijital Yönetimle Paradoksal İlişkisi 713**
Öğr. Gör. Dr. Naci Atalay Davutoğlu
- Carry Trade Türkiye için Tehdit Mi Fırsat Mı? Teorik ve Ampirik Analiz..... 724**
Prof. Dr. Utku Altunöz
- Çevrim İçi Kumar Bağımlılığı ve Bağlanma Stilleri Arasındaki İlişkinin İncelenmesi736**
Psikolog Dicle Adıgüzel
Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Naif Ergün
- Dijital Yönetim ve Bilgi Çağının Yakınsal İlişkisi 746**
Öğr. Gör. Dr. Naci Atalay Davutoğlu
- Ebû Vâkıd el-Leysî'nin Hayatı ve el-Kutubu's-Sitte'de Yer Alan Hadis Rivâyetleri Üzerine Bir Araştırma 755**
Doç. Dr. Erdoğan Köycü
Uzman Eymen Hıdır
- Gazze Nasıl Gıda Çölüne Dönüştürüldü?..... 768**
Doç. Dr. Hülya Yiğit Özüdoğru
- Yükseköğretimde Modernleşme Projesi Olarak Dârülfünûn 779**
Doç. Dr. Halil İbrahim Çelik

Hasan e-Bennâ'nın Muhtasar Hadîs Usûlü Adlı Eserinde Hadis İstılahlarına Dair Değerlendirmelerine Bir Bakış..... 794

Doç. Dr. Erdoğan Köycü

The Distributional Consequences of Globalization: A Nonlinear Analysis of Canada's Economic, Social, and Political Dimensions 807

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kemal Erkişi

The Impact of Socio-Economic Factors on Air Quality: The Case of China 818

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kemal Erkişi

Kent Yoksulluğu ve Kadın 830

Öğr. Gör. Dr. Talha Turhan

Doktora Öğrencisi Duygu Karakaş Aydın

İranlı Bir Âlim: Molla Muhammed Bakır Balekî (1897-1972) ve el-Mantık'ul-mehdevî Adlı Eseri* 846

Doktora Öğrencisi Gülistan Güvener

Sâmânî Emirlerinden Nasr b. Ahmed ile Oğlu Nuh b. Nasr'ın Bâtınîler'le İlişkisi 858

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Mustafa Keskin

Osmanlı Ceza Muhakemesi Hukukunda Seri Yargılama 874

Prof. Dr. Ömer Menekşe

Milli Fabrika Formu Çerçevesinde Paşabahçe Şişecam'ın İlk Yıllarında İşgücü ve Çalışma Koşulları..... 893

Prof. Dr. Hatice Özutku

Doktora Öğrencisi Okşan Algur

Peygamberimizin (S.A.S.) Aile ve Yakınları İle Olan İletişimi..... 901

Doç. Dr. Erdoğan Köycü

Peygamberimizin (S.A.S.) Bireylerle Olan İletişimi 913

Doç. Dr. Erdoğan Köycü

Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Ayşegül Küçükdeniz

Nontraditional Diplomacy- Environmental Diplomacy Initiatives of China in Central Asia 921

Ph.D Sharifa Giritlioglu

İtalya'nın Turizm Politikası ve Grosseto Destinasyonu..... 934

Prof. Dr. Sibel Mehter Aykın

Bir Esbâb-ı Nüzûl Çalışması: Ehl-i Kitab'ın Sebeb-i Nüzûle Konu Olduğu Âyetler (Vâhidî'nin *Esbâbü nüzûli'l-Kur'ân*'ı Bağlamında)..... 950

Doç. Dr. Nurdoğan Türk

Türkiye'de Yerel Yönetim Bakanlığı Denemeleri ve Bakanlığın Önemi..... 980

Uzman Handan Yılmaz

Kur'ân-ı Kerim'in Bilimsel Mucizeleri 996

Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Zehra Beker

Nontraditional Diplomacy- Environmental Diplomacy Initiatives of China in Central Asia

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Abstract

This study investigates China's environmental diplomacy efforts in Central Asia, a region grappling with severe environmental issues like water shortages, desertification, and climate change effects. Recently, China has heightened its involvement with Central Asian countries through various environmental accords and collaborative projects to tackle these problems. By examining China's bilateral and multilateral environmental agreements and the incorporation of green policies into the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), this paper assesses how environmental diplomacy strategically advances China's foreign policy objectives in the region.

Through case studies of specific environmental agreements, it is argued that China's environmental diplomacy in Central Asia functions both as a strategy to reduce environmental harm and as a means to increase its influence in the area. These efforts have encouraged regional collaboration and enhanced China's global image, yet they also face criticism, particularly concerning sustainability and potential resource exploitation.

This research ultimately enhances understanding of environmental diplomacy as a form of soft power, assisting China in strengthening its role as a significant entity in Central Asia while addressing urgent ecological challenges. The paper concludes with policy recommendations to improve environmental collaboration between China and Central Asian countries and proposes areas for further study on the long-term impacts of China's environmental initiatives in the region.

Keywords: *Central Asia, China, Environmental Diplomacy, Sustainable development, Belt and Road Initiative*

Geleneksel Olmayan Diplomasi - Çin'in Orta Asya'da Çevre Diplomasisi Girişimleri

Özet

Bu çalışmada, Çin'in su kıtlığı, çölleşme ve iklim değişikliğinin etkileri gibi ciddi çevresel sorunlarla boğuşan bir bölge olan Orta Asya'ya yönelik çevre diplomasisi araştırılmaktadır. Son zamanlarda Çin, çeşitli çevre anlaşmaları ve bu sorunların üstesinden gelmek için ortak projeler yoluyla Orta Asya ülkeleriyle olan ilişkilerini artırmıştır. Bu çerçevede makale, Çin'in ikili ve çok taraflı çevre anlaşmalarını ve yeşil politikaların Bir Kuşak ve Bir Yol Girişimi'ne (BRI) dahil edilmesini inceleyerek, çevre diplomasisinin Çin'in bölgedeki dış politika hedeflerini stratejik olarak nasıl ilerlettiğini değerlendirmektedir. Belirli çevresel projelerle

ilgili vaka araştırmaları yöntemiyle, Çin'in Orta Asya'daki çevre diplomasisinin hem çevresel zararı azaltma stratejisi hem de bölgedeki etkisini artırma aracı olarak işlev gördüğü öne sürülmektedir. Bu çabalar bölgesel işbirliğini teşvik etmekte ve Çin'in küresel imajını güçlendirmektedir, ancak özellikle sürdürülebilirlik ve potansiyel kaynak kullanımı ile ilgili eleştirilerle de karşı karşıya kalmıştır. Bu araştırma nihayetinde çevre diplomasisinin bir tür yumuşak güç olarak anlaşılmasını geliştirerek, Çin'in acil ekolojik zorlukları ele alırken Orta Asya'da önemli bir aktör olarak rolünü güçlendirmesine yardımcı olduğunu savunmaktadır. Makalenin sonuç kısmında, Çin ile Orta Asya ülkeleri arasındaki çevresel işbirliğini iyileştirmeye yönelik politika önerileri ve Çin'in bölgedeki çevresel girişimlerinin uzun vadeli etkileri üzerine daha fazla çalışma için alanlar önerilmektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Orta Asya, Çin, Çevre Diplomasisi, Sürdürülebilir kalkınma, Bir Kuşak ve Bir Yol Girişimi

Introduction

In the context of increasing global environmental challenges, environmental diplomacy has emerged as a significant form of international cooperation. Unlike traditional diplomacy, which is focused primarily on political and economic relations, environmental diplomacy seeks to address global ecological issues through collaborative efforts between nations. This form of diplomacy has become especially relevant in regions like Central Asia. Central Asia, comprising the post-Soviet republics of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan, has faced severe environmental challenges in recent decades. These challenges have limited the socio-economic development of the region (Pobedinsky & Shestak, 2020, p. 70). Environmental problems such as water scarcity, desertification, biodiversity loss, inadequate waste management, energy inefficiency, and the effects of climate change pose have undermined the region's stability and security (Prodanova et al., 2020, p. 31; Tookey, 2007, p. 192).

To address these pressing environmental issues, the Central Asian countries and China have engaged in various diplomatic initiatives aimed at fostering regional cooperation and improving environmental governance (Pobedinsky & Shestak, 2020, p. 75; Prodanova et al., 2020, p. 32). Owing to the swift advancement of China's economy and the substantial increase in its population over the last few decades, ecological issues have emerged in both its domestic and foreign policies. Presently, China grapples with numerous environmental challenges, the most prominent being pollution, destructive natural and human-induced processes (such as accelerated erosion and pasture degradation), and a rise in the frequency and severity of natural disasters. Upon recognizing that economic prosperity is unattainable without addressing environmental issues, the PRC authorities-initiated efforts to develop the environmental sector. Enhancing the environmental situation necessitates international cooperation, as these problems are not confined to a single nation but impact the global ecosystem (Yasmin, 2021, p. 5).

Despite the apparent benefits of China's environmental diplomacy, these efforts have also raised concerns. Critics argue that while China's projects may mitigate some environmental issues, they may also serve as instrument of soft power, helping China to assert its dominance in the region. Questions about the sustainability of these initiatives and potential resource

exploitation have also surfaced, highlighting the complexity of China's role as both a regional partner and rising global power.

This study investigates China's environmental diplomacy initiatives in Central Asia, examining how these efforts contribute to both environmental protection and China's strategic interests. By analysing bilateral and multilateral environmental agreements. As well as China's integration of green policies into the BRI, this research seeks to assess the dual nature of China's environmental diplomacy.

This research has the following objectives: the first, to study the scope and nature of China's environmental diplomacy efforts in Central Asia; the second, to evaluate the impact of China's environmental diplomacy on regional cooperation and environmental sustainability; the third, to assess the criticisms and challenges associated with China's environmental diplomacy, particularly in terms of resource exploitation and long-term sustainability; and the last to propose policy recommendations to improve cooperation between China and Central Asian countries.

In light of this background the research question which arises is the follows: (1) What are the main environmental diplomacy initiatives led by China in Central Asia? (2) How Central Asian states view China's environmental efforts? (3) What criticism exist regarding the sustainability and potential resource exploitation associated with China's environmental projects in the region? An the last (4) How can China and Central Asian nations enhance their environmental collaboration for long-term ecological sustainability and mutual benefit?

The findings of this research are significant for both scholars and policymakers. By exploring how environmental diplomacy serves as a tool for both ecological cooperation and geopolitical influence, this study provides insights into the role of nontraditional diplomacy in international relations. Moreover, understanding China's strategic use of environmental diplomacy will help Central Asian countries and international actors craft better policies for sustainable development. This research also contributes to the growing body of literature on the Belt and Road Initiative, specially regarding its environmental implications.

Literature Review

China's BRI in Central Asia aims to enhance infrastructure and economic development. Several of studies have explored the environmental and economic implications of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) in Central Asia. For example, Rimmer's (2018) study examines the economic and international dimensions of China's BRI. However Rimmer highlights that BRI aims to establish a framework for interconnecting China with Russia, Central Asian countries, Southeast Asia, West Asia, South Asia, and Eastern Europe (Rimmer, 2018). Also P. Cai (2017) highlights that while the BRI is often viewed through a geopolitical lens, some key drivers are rooted in China's economic concerns. The paper also notes that the success of the BRI hinges on factors like the willingness of other countries to absorb China's excess capacity and the ability of Chinese bankers to navigate complex investment environments (Cai, 2017, p. 15). While Vakulchuk et al. (2019) in his research analyses how the BRI has impacted Central Asian perception of China. In the research authors particularly interested in understanding local actors' perspectives on the BRI and how it has affected economic interaction, infrastructure projects, and educational initiatives between China and the five Central Asian states (Vakulchuk & Overland, 2019). These studies have highlighted both the potential

benefits and risks of increased economic cooperation and infrastructure development in the region.

On one hand, the Belt and Road Initiative has been seen as an opportunity to promote sustainable development and enhance regional environmental cooperation in Central Asia (Rimmer, 2018, p. 8). By investing in renewable energy, improving waste management, and supporting biodiversity conservation, China's environmental diplomacy initiatives have the potential to yield economic dividends for the region through improved resource management and reduced environmental degradation (Pobedinsky & Shestak, 2020, p. 10). Gao and Liu (2024) in their research asserts that China's renewable energy investment in Central Asia contributes to the Central Asian countries' greenhouse gas emission reduction targets and sustainable development goals, while also addressing the problems and barriers that have emerged in China's Green Silk Roads and Belt Economic Initiative in the region (Gao & Liu, 2024, p. 485). Research paper by M.Maliszewska and A.Van Der Mensbrugge (2019) that analyzes the economic, social, and environmental impacts of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). The authors use a general equilibrium (CGE) model to estimate the impact of the BRI on trade, growth, poverty, and greenhouse gas emissions in countries participating in the initiative. The study suggests that the BRI will bring significant benefits by increasing global income, reducing poverty, and stimulating economic growth, especially in East Asian countries. However, the authors also note that some countries not participating in the BRI may face problems due to trade diversion (Maliszewska & Van Der Mensbrugge, 2019).

On the other hand, there are concerns that rapid economic growth and infrastructure expansion under the Belt and Road framework could exacerbate environmental problems and undermine sustainability in Central Asia. Potential risks include increased greenhouse gas emissions, habitat fragmentation, and overexploitation of natural resources. Tracy et al. (2017) claims that while China has made strides in implementing ecological modernization domestically, particularly in industries exposed to Western markets, this approach doesn't appear to be reflected in its planning of the Silk Road Economic Belt. The authors observe a discrepancy between China's domestic and international environmental approach. While domestically, China promoting 'ecological civilization', its overseas development projects, especially those related to the Silk Road Economic Belt, show little consideration for strategic environmental impact assessment (Tracy et al., 2017, p. 68). According to the the Horizon Scan of the BRI made by Hughes et al. (2020) identified 11 key issues associated with the BRI, covering both environmental and social aspects. The authors express skepticism about whether China will implement the ecological redline concept within the BRI, and if so, how this approach can be effectively governed in the more complex context of international settings (Hughes et al., 2020, p. 9). According to Sidle (2020), the proliferation of spur roads and resource extraction projects associated with the Belt and Road could lead to severe environmental degradation, including landslides, erosion, and pollution of river systems (Sidle, 2020).

Data and Method

To address the research objectives, this study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data from various sources. The primary data sources include: 1. Government reports and policy documents from the Central Asian countries and China on

environmental cooperation and economic development initiatives. Academic journal articles and conference proceedings that analyze the environmental impacts of China's engagement in Central Asia 3. Reports and datasets from international organizations such as the World Bank, Asian Development Bank, and UN Environment Programme on regional environmental trends; 4. News articles from reputable media outlets covering the evolving diplomatic and economic relationships between China and Central Asia.

1. Overview of Environmental Agreements in China-Central Asia Partnerships

China and Central Asian states have engaged in various bilateral and multilateral environmental agreements (Table 1.) aimed at addressing environmental challenges and fostering sustainable development.

Table 1. Bilateral Environmental Agreements between China and Central Asian States

No	Date	Countries	Titel of the agreement	Summary of the agreement
1	2015	Kazakhstan - China	Joint Declaration on New Stage of Comprehensive Strategic Partnership Between the People's Republic of China and the Republic of Kazakhstan ¹	This agreement focuses on enhancing cooperation in various sectors, including industrialization and investment, which encompasses renewable energy projects
2	2024	Kazakhstan - China	Renewable Energy Cooperation Agreement ²	Highlighted in the strategic partnership discussions, this agreement aims to promote green energy initiatives between the two nations
3	2022	Uzbekistan - China	Comprehensive Strategic Partnership Agreement ³	This agreement emphasizes green energy as a priority area for collaboration, leading to the signing of an intergovernmental agreement on renewable energy

¹ Ministry of Foreign Affairs People's Republic of China (2015) Joint Declaration on New Stage of Comprehensive Strategic Partnership Between the People's Republic of China and the Republic of Kazakhstan (Full Text), https://www.mfa.gov.cn/eng/zy/jj/2015zt/jnkzsl70zn/202406/t20240606_11381460.html, Accession date: 28.08.2028

² CNPC (2024) CNPC and Kazakh partners ink a series of agreements on energy cooperation, <https://www.cnpc.com.cn/en/nr2024/202407/289d67026cbb4c8fa4d9c5611bf01930.shtml>, Accession date: 28.08.2024

³ President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2022) A Set of Documents Aimed at Strengthening the Uzbek-Chinese Comprehensive Strategic Partnership Signed, <https://president.uz/en/lists/view/5519>, Accession date: 28.08.2024

				cooperation in 2023
4	2024	Tajikistan-China	Comprehensive strategic cooperative partnership Agreement ⁴	Tajikistan has engaged in dialogues with China focusing on environmental sustainability and resource management, particularly concerning water resources in the region
5	2023	Kyrgyzstan - China	Comprehensive strategic cooperative partnership Agreement ⁵	Similar to Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan has entered into discussions with China regarding environmental cooperation, particularly in managing shared water resources and addressing ecological challenges
6	2023	Turkmenistan-China	Comprehensive Strategic Partnership Agreement ⁶	Both countries pledged to explore additional opportunities in renewable energy and the development of whole industry chains, particularly in the natural gas sector

Note: The table was compiled by the author based on the research findings

The "Joint Declaration on a New Stage of Comprehensive Strategic Partnership" between China and Kazakhstan was signed during President Nursultan Nazarbayev's visit to China from August 30 to September 3, 2015. Both nations committed to upholding the "Treaty of Good-Neighborliness and Friendly Cooperation" (signed in 2002) and the "Joint Statement on Comprehensive Strategic Partnership" (signed in 2011) and other bilateral treaties, focusing on strengthening mutual trust, political cooperation, and contributions toward regional and global peace and sustainable development. Additionally, both countries pledged to prioritize environmental considerations in joint production and investment projects, encouraging the

⁴ Ministry of Foreign Affairs People's Republic of China (2024) Xi Jinping and Tajik President Emomali Rahmon Jointly Meet the Press, https://www.mfa.gov.cn/eng/xw/zyxw/202407/t20240715_11454055.html Accession date: 28.08.2024

⁵ The State Council the People's Republic of China (2023) Chinese, Kyrgyz Presidents hold talks, elevate bilateral relationship. https://english.www.gov.cn/news/202305/18/content_WS6465b901c6d03ffcca6ed27d.html , Accession date 28.08.2024

⁶ National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC) People's Republic of China (2023) China, Turkmenistan Upgrade Ties. https://en.ndrc.gov.cn/news/mediarources/202301/t20230131_1348601.html , Accession date: 28.08.2024

adoption of advanced, energy-efficient technologies to foster high-value, competitive production (Ministry of Foreign Affairs People's Republic of China, 2015).

In 2015, consultations began on a draft agreement regarding the allocation of water resources from cross-border rivers, which aimed to elevate bilateral cooperation on water resource management and environmental protection. Both sides are committed to advancing this agreement to enhance cooperation on sustainable water usage. Discussions also included the potential integration of the China-Kazakhstan Environmental Protection Cooperation Committee into the broader China-Kazakhstan Cooperation Committee framework to facilitate collaborative environmental initiatives.

In 2024, during President Xi Jinping's visit to Kazakhstan, the China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC) signed a framework agreement with Kazakhstan's Ministry of Energy to strengthen cooperation in the energy sector. This included a collaboration with Samruk-Kazyna JSC to develop a 400 MW renewable energy project and further cooperation with KazMunayGas (KMG) in oil and gas sectors, covering petroleum exploration, refining, and new energy. These agreements reflect a commitment to expand cooperation on clean energy, technology transfer, and environmental protection across the energy sector (CNPC, 2024).

Following productive talks on September 15, 2022, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan and President Xi Jinping of China signed a joint statement outlining agreements to advance their comprehensive strategic partnership. As part of this high-level visit, 15 documents were signed, including memoranda on promoting investment in green development, cooperation in mineral development, and construction. Trade and investment agreements totaling \$15 billion further solidified these commitments, particularly in environmentally responsible development and sustainable resource use (President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2022).

During Xi Jinping's state visit to Tajikistan in July 2024, the two sides agreed to focus on high-quality cooperation under the Belt and Road Initiative, aiming to align development strategies to advance modernization. China expressed readiness to support Tajikistan's transit potential and upgrade economic cooperation, especially in new energy, digital economy, artificial intelligence, and e-commerce. China and Tajikistan also plan to deepen people-to-people exchanges, facilitating partnerships in education, traditional medicine, and cultural exchange to strengthen their ties. These commitments highlight mutual efforts to integrate sustainable practices within economic development and foster cultural and technological exchange (Ministry of Foreign Affairs People's Republic of China, 2024).

At the China-Central Asia Summit in May 2023, Kyrgyzstan's President Sadyr Japarov and President Xi Jinping of China announced an elevation in their bilateral relationship, establishing a comprehensive strategic partnership. The two nations agreed on mutual support for sovereignty and territorial integrity and committed to expanding cooperation in green energy, climate change mitigation, and the establishment of cross-border trade centers. The summit emphasized collaboration in areas such as infrastructure, energy, digitalization, and tourism, underscoring the shared goal of sustainable economic growth (The State Council the People's Republic of China, 2022).

During Turkmenistan's President Serdar Berdimukhamedov's first official visit to China in January 2023, the two presidents exchanged views on bilateral and international cooperation,

resulting in several agreements, including those on green development, digital economy, and health. Energy collaboration remains a priority, with natural gas cooperation forming the cornerstone of China-Turkmenistan relations. Both countries pledged to explore additional opportunities in renewable energy and the development of whole industry chains, particularly in the natural gas sector. China and Turkmenistan also agreed to enhance cooperation on security issues, including biosecurity, law enforcement, and counter-terrorism, which supports the broader security and stability of their partnership(NDRC, 2023).

The China-Central Asia Gas Pipeline, jointly developed by China and Turkmenistan, exemplifies their commitment to sustainable energy solutions, supplying natural gas to over 500 million people across multiple Chinese provinces(Cutler, 2018).

2. The View of Central Asian States on China's Environmental Diplomacy

China's environmental diplomacy has bolstered its image as a committed global actor in sustainable development and ecological stewardship. In April 2019, China outlined a vision for a greener Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), focusing on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, controlling pollution, and preserving biodiversity. Its decision to halt the construction of new coal power plants abroad marks a transformative shift towards sustainable investment and aligns with international climate objectives, underscoring China's dedication to responsible development practices(Jackson, 2020, p. 3).

China has also taken a proactive stance in global environmental governance, illustrated by its active role in the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework(UNEP, 2022). This engagement not only highlights China's capacity to tackle environmental issues but also reinforces its leadership in addressing global ecological challenges. Distinctly, China's environmental diplomacy often follows a non-interventionist approach, refraining from imposing the conditionalities typically associated with Western aid(Khan et al., 2018). This model resonates well with developing countries, which favor partnerships without political stipulations, thereby enhancing China's soft power and appeal.

Environmental initiatives under the BRI frequently incorporate cultural exchange, fostering mutual understanding and reinforcing positive narratives about China's commitment to global environmental governance(Cai, 2017). Domestically, China's progress in combating desertification has also lent credibility to its international environmental efforts, as China shares this expertise with other nations, addressing critical environmental concerns on a global scale.

Furthermore, China's ambitious climate targets, including peaking carbon emissions by 2030 and achieving carbon neutrality by 2060, signify a serious commitment to combating climate change(Gao & Liu, 2024). This dedication places China as a vital contributor to international climate initiatives, aligning it with global efforts to meet shared climate goals and cementing its role in climate negotiations.

3. Environmental Diplomacy and Central Asia's Response

The environmental cooperation initiatives within the BRI framework have produced varied and multifaceted outcomes in Central Asia. On one hand, these projects have fostered deeper regional economic integration and infrastructural development, bringing substantial economic advantages to Central Asian countries(Eurasianet, 2024; Ministry of Finance of Kyrgyz

Republic, 2023; The Astana Times, 2023). The harmonization of regulatory standards and reduction of trade barriers have strengthened regional interdependence and encouraged cooperative efforts among Central Asian states to tackle shared challenges (Nabiyeva, 2019).

However, the rapid expansion of infrastructure and resource extraction has also introduced significant environmental risks, such as ecosystem degradation, increased pollution, and resource depletion (Hughes et al., 2020; Teo et al., 2019). The balance between economic growth and environmental sustainability remains a complex issue in the region, leading to both positive engagement and mounting skepticism toward China's involvement.

Central Asian states generally recognize China as a critical economic partner, particularly in terms of investment, trade, and infrastructure development (Nabiyeva, 2019; Toktogulova & Zhuang, 2020). The BRI has spurred considerable Chinese investments in energy and infrastructure, which are essential for economic progress in nations like Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan. Since President Shavkat Mirziyoyev assumed office, Uzbekistan has experienced a marked increase in Chinese investment, reflecting a more favorable stance on economic cooperation with China (Xi Jinping Holds Talks with President Shavkat Mirziyoyev of Uzbekistan, 2024). Additionally, the development of roads, railways, and energy pipelines financed by China has enhanced connectivity across Central Asia and to global markets, a development viewed positively for its potential to expand trade and benefit local economies. Given regional security concerns, especially regarding terrorism and instability in Afghanistan, Central Asian countries value China's security contributions through the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), which they see as stabilizing forces for the region (Zhai, 2018).

Despite the economic benefits, a growing undercurrent of skepticism has emerged due to environmental concerns associated with Chinese investments, particularly in BRI projects (Vakulchuk & Overland, 2019). Local NGOs have raised issues related to insufficient environmental impact assessments and a lack of public involvement in decision-making processes, contributing to a rise in anti-China sentiment. Protests against specific projects have been spurred by fears of ecological harm and social disruption. A 2020 study showed that only a small percentage of citizens in Kazakhstan (7%) and Kyrgyzstan (9%) expressed strong support for Chinese infrastructure and energy projects, reflecting increasing unease over China's influence. Transparency and governance concerns are particularly significant, as perceptions persist that Chinese companies often operate with minimal transparency and limited adherence to local regulations. Reports indicate that Chinese firms may not fully inform local communities or engage in consultations, which has fostered mistrust and resistance to Chinese initiatives (Koçak & Gürel Yeşilçimen, 2024).

Lastly, some Central Asian nations express caution over potential economic dependence on China, especially in light of large infrastructure loans. Concerns about "debt traps" have prompted calls for a reassessment of cooperation policies to ensure balanced and mutually beneficial engagements without risking national economic autonomy (Nabiyeva, 2019).

Conclusion

China's environmental initiatives reinforce its position as a committed global actor in sustainable development and ecological governance. Through active participation in international frameworks, sharing innovative environmental solutions, and supporting

developing nations, China not only addresses pressing environmental challenges but also strengthens its soft power globally. These efforts foster a more favorable perception of China as it seeks to lead in global environmental governance while cultivating cooperative relationships with other nations.

This study has shown that the environmental and social effects of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and associated infrastructure development in Central Asia are intricate and multifaceted. While these projects have stimulated economic growth and regional integration, there are notable environmental and governance challenges that must be addressed to sustain collaboration moving forward. Key issues include concerns over transparency, regulatory compliance, and the long-term ecological impact of these initiatives, as some argue that economic priorities often overshadow ecological sustainability. This has led to calls for more thorough environmental assessments and stronger public involvement in BRI-related decision-making.

The findings underscore the tension between the economic benefits and the environmental and social costs of these projects, pointing to the need for a more comprehensive and sustainable approach to regional infrastructure development. The conclusions align closely with previous research on China's regional initiatives in Central Asia, which similarly highlights the need to balance economic objectives with environmental and social considerations. For instance, research by Lechner et al. (2020) noted that the expansion of infrastructure and resource exploitation in sensitive ecosystems, such as the Pamirs and Tien Shan ranges, threatens unique biodiversity and delicate environmental balances.

This study suggests several policy recommendations for Central Asian countries and China to mitigate the environmental impact of BRI projects: (1) Strengthening Environmental Impact Assessments and Sustainability Standards: Central Asian countries and China should collaborate to create and enforce rigorous environmental protocols and sustainability standards for all infrastructure projects associated with the BRI and related efforts. (2) Promoting Sustainable Resource Management: Joint policies and practices are needed to ensure the responsible use of natural resources, safeguard fragile ecosystems, and prevent pollution and environmental degradation in the region. (3) Enhancing Regional Coordination and Knowledge-Sharing: Establishing robust mechanisms for regional coordination, information-sharing, and the exchange of best practices on environmental protection and sustainable development will be essential. (4) Prioritizing Inclusive Development and Community Engagement: Infrastructure projects should be designed with input from local communities to address their needs, uphold their rights, and minimize negative social impacts. (5) Strengthening Environmental Governance and Judicial Oversight: Central Asian countries should improve their legal frameworks for environmental protection and ensure strong judicial oversight to hold project developers accountable for environmental and social impacts.

Implementing these policy recommendations is crucial to ensuring that the economic benefits of the BRI and similar initiatives are balanced with the need to protect the environment and promote sustainable development in Central Asia.

This study has several limitations. It primarily examines the environmental and social impacts of the BRI in Central Asia, without fully addressing the economic and geopolitical dimensions of these initiatives. The analysis relies on a limited set of sources, so additional relevant

research may not be included. Furthermore, the findings may not be generalizable across all regions involved in the BRI, as the environmental and social impacts vary by local context and project specifics.

Future research could address these limitations by broadening the scope to include economic and geopolitical factors, incorporating a wider range of data for a more comprehensive view, and conducting in-depth case studies on specific projects or regions to understand local dynamics and challenges. Research could also explore the role of local and indigenous communities in shaping the development and implementation of BRI projects. Expanding the research agenda in these ways will be essential for developing more sustainable and effective regional development strategies in Central Asia and along the broader Belt and Road.

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